

Spectroscopic Simulations for the Evaluation of Systematics in Euclid with SPRING

Passalacqua F.^{1, 2}, Troja A.^{1, 2}, Fumana M.³, Paganin L.^{4, 5}, Risso I.^{4, 5}, and Scodreggio M.³

¹*Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia “G. Galilei”, Università degli Studi di Padova, Via Marzolo 8, I-35131, Padova, Italy*

²*INFN-Padova, Via Marzolo 8, I-35132, Padova, Italy*

³*INAF-IASF Milano, Via Alfonso Corti 12, 20133 Milano, Italy*

⁴*Dipartimento di Fisica, Università degli Studi di Genova, Via Dodecaneso 33, I-16146 Genova, Italy*

⁵*INFN Sezione di Genova, Via Dodecaneso 33, I-16146 Genova, Italy*

Euclid is a European Space Agency (ESA) mission, designed to investigate the nature of Dark Energy and Dark Matter. It will measure the positions, shapes, and colors for billions of galaxies, and also redshift for a subset of tens of millions of those galaxies to map the matter distribution with unprecedented accuracy. The satellite launch took place in July 2023, and the data taking will last for six years covering one-third of the entire sky.

To attain the desired level of precision in parameter estimation, meticulous management of systematic effects is required. These effects have both hardware and astrophysical origins: the former includes detector non-idealities and telescope response; the latter includes cosmic rays, background light, and signal contamination from different sources.

In order to quantify the efficiency in the redshift reconstruction, we have developed the Spectroscopic Pipeline Runner and INput Generator (SPRING) which runs pixel-level simulations and performs the data processing through Euclid spectroscopic pipeline.

SPRING is designed to use the Euclid official pipelines while simultaneously providing users with the capability to independently and easily manage instrumental and environmental effects. This versatile tool enables the simulation of both realistic and non-astrophysical exposures, making it a suitable instrument for quantifying systematics impacting redshift measurements.